

Announcement

High Performance Computing Technologies in Finances

15-16 July 2013
Genexis Theatre, Fusionopolis,
Singapore

The finance industry requires in-depth computational modelling of market conditions, pricing models, risk models, and contingencies. To compete internationally, banks and investment companies must perform frequent analysis of current conditions in order to accurately assess risk and benefit of different investment, strategies as well as loan and investment instrument pricing strategies that maximise profitability while minimising risk of loss.

This symposium serves to demonstrate how technologies originating in High Performance Computing are being absorbed in daily practice in the financial industry. We demonstrate current HPC technologies applicable and beneficial to computational finance and seek financial industry collaboration to work on urgent and timely problems in quickly and accurately performing financial analysis and big data processing.

Registration is open at www.tinyurl.com/hpc-in-finances

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Day one (15 July)			
08:30 – 09:00	Registration		
09:00 – 09:05	Welcome address: Dr Marek T. Michalewicz , Dr Kyle Rupnow		
09:05 – 09:20	Welcome speech by Guest of Honour: Mr Leong Sing Chiong, Executive Director, Financial Centre Development Department, Monetary Authority of Singapore		
09:20 – 10:05	Keynote 1: Prof Mark Salmon, Cambridge University & Imperial College of London <i>Title: The Critical Role of Modelling Trading Intensity in Algorithmic Trading</i>		
10:05 – 10:45	Hideyuki Torii, Managing Director, Numerical Technologies <i>Title: Computational Finance, Portfolio Management, and HPC</i>		
10:45 – 11:00	Tea break		
11:00 – 11:30	Stephen Weston, Chief Development Officer, Maxeler <i>Title: Transforming uncertainty into strategy using hardware.</i>		
11:30 – 12:00	Dr Eng Lim Goh, SVP & Chief Technology Officer, SGI <i>Title: HPC, Big Data & Analytics in Finance</i>		
12:00 – 12:30	Kim Ong, Business Development Director, Triaset Pte Ltd <i>Title: Accelerating Market Risk</i>		
12:30 – 13:30	Lunch		
13:30 – 18:00	Parallel Tracks : Hands-on Practical Workshops		
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Day two (16 July)			
09:00 – 09:45	Keynote 2: Kiran Narsu, Global Head of Financial Services , YarcData <i>Title: Augment Your Analytics Ecosystem Through Scalable Graph Analytics</i>		
09:45 – 10:30	R. Ravichandran, Director of Enterprise Solutions Sales APAC, Intel <i>Title: Driving Industrial Innovation on the Path to Exascale</i>		
10:30 – 11:00	Tea break		
11:00 – 11:30	Dr Oliver Chen, Deputy Director of Education and Industry Outreach, NUS Risk Management Institute <i>Title: GPUs for Computational Finance: Credit Risk Applications</i>		
11:30 – 12:00	Gabriel Sallah, IBM Platform Computing GMU Architect for Financial Services <i>Title: HPC in Finance - 10 years and counting , Past, Present and Tomorrow</i>		
12:00 – 12:30	Prof David Thomas, Imperial College, London <i>Title: Beyond HFT: FPGAs for analytics</i>		
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